

CORRELATION BETWEEN FATTY LIVER DISEASE AND CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE

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Abstract

Background: Chronic kidney disease incidence and cardiovascular disease are independently correlated with non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease. If NAFLD is linked to the metabolic syndrome, it could become a serious public health issue. It has not been determined whether NAFLD and its outcomes in patients with advanced CKD are related. This study assessed the frequency of NAFLD in a sizable secondary care CKD population and examined its effects on mortality, cardiovascular, and renal outcomes.

Methods: This Case Control study was conducted at the Radiology department of Meer Khan Family & Children Hospital. Patients with the ages of 35 to 85 who underwent a renal ultrasound. Data were collected with the help of convenient sampling technique. Individuals with two bilateral, symmetric kidneys (NAFLAD CVD) are included in the study and pregnant women were excluded from the study.

Results: According to the study, almost all of participants had mild to moderate fatty liver disease, with 45% being Grade 1 fatty liver, 36% having Grade 2, and 19% having Grade 3. Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) was also found in 56% of patients, with early stages being more common. The findings suggested a possible link between increased frequency of CKD, especially in Grade 3, and higher fatty liver grades. While there was no significant correlation between fatty liver grades and CKD stages ($p = 0.742$), chi-square tests revealed a significant relationship between fatty liver grading and the existence of CKD ($p = 0.026$), suggesting a possible link between fatty liver advancement and CKD.

Conclusion: Study concluded that CKD has significant association with fatty liver grading

INTRODUCTION

Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is the most frequent cause of abnormal liver biochemistry tests globally, but clinical practice under recognized it because of the absence of symptoms in the early stages of the disease. (1) It includes a broad spectrum of diseases, such major fibrosis, cirrhosis, steatohepatitis, and simple steatosis. (2) Over the past ten years, NAFLD has grown into the leading cause of chronic liver disease globally, with a marked increase in prevalence among individuals below 45. (3) The variation in prevalence estimates relates to the methods used in the diagnosis of NAFLD. (4) NAFLD has been recognized as an important cause of end-stage liver disease, with 25% of patients suffering cryptogenic cirrhosis and HCC.(5) In along with end-stage liver disease, NAFLD is associated with metabolic variables like central obesity, insulin resistance, arterial hypertension, and hypertriglyceridemia. NAFLD has been linked to a variety of extrahepatic diseases such as sarcopenia, type 2 diabetes, cancer, and cardiovascular disease.(5),(6)

The stage of liver fibrosis is associated with the risk of CKD in patients with NAFLD is not fully clarified. (7) (8). The NAFLD fibrosis score (NAFLD-FS) was created in 2007 to gauge the severity of NAFLD patients, and it has been confirmed among individuals a range of backgrounds and ages with varying metabolic factor status. (9) (10). If NAFLD-FS is less than 1.454 and greater than 0.676, respectively, it is possible to predict the presence or absence of significant fibrosis with an accuracy rate

greater than 85%.(11) (12) In this study was to clarify the connection between the prevalence of NAFLD and CKD. Using NAFLD-FS, we also assessed the correlation between CKD and liver fibrosis stage in NAFLD individuals (13) (14). Our study was conducted to gain insight into the prevalence of NAFLD in advanced CKD and to investigate whether NAFLD had any influence on three primary outcomes (i) all-cause mortality,(ii) non-fatal cardio vascular events (NFCVEs) and (iii) rate of progression of CKD in a large cohort of non-dialysis CKD patient. (15)

Methodology:

This Case Control study was conducted at the Radiology department of Meer khan Children & Family Hospital. Patients with the ages of 35 to 85 who underwent a renal ultrasound. This study utilizing a Toshiba Xario XG color Doppler ultrasound device with a convex transducer operating at 3-5 MHz. All patients will be scanned while partially full in the prone, lateral, and supine positions. A detailed patient history was followed by a comprehensive clinical examination Data were collected with the help of convenient sampling technique. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Individuals with two bilateral, symmetric kidneys (NAFLAD CVD) are included in the study and pregnant women were excluded from the study. The study participants gave their verbal, voluntary consent.

Results:

Table No.1

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Female	50	25.0
	Male	150	75.0
	Total	200	100.0
Valid	1.00	90	45.0
	2.00	72	36.0
	3.00	38	19.0
	Total	200	100.0
Valid	No	88	44.0
	Yes	112	56.0
	Total	200	100.0

Valid	.00	87	43.5
	1.00	58	29.0
	2.00	31	15.5
	3.00	23	11.5
	Total	200	100.0

The first describe the gender distribution, comprising 50 females (25%) and 150 males (75%) and In the 2nd which has a grade from 1.00 to 3.00, 90 participants (45%) scored a score of 1.00, 72 participants (36%) scored 2.00, and 38 participants (19%) scored 3.00. In the third 88 participants (44%) responded with "No," while 112 participants

(56%) responded with "Yes." The fourth one describe the frequency of responses on from 1.00 (58 participants, or 29%). The numbers decrease for higher scores: 2.00 was given by 31 participants (15.5%), 3.00 by 23 participants (11.5%), and only one participant (0.5%) scored 4.00.

Table No.2

		CKD			Total	P _ value
		No	Yes			
Fatty Liver Grading	1.00	Count	47	43	90	0.026
		% of Total	23.5%	21.5%	45.0%	
	2.00	Count	31	41	72	
		% of Total	15.5%	20.5%	36.0%	
	3.00	Count	10	28	38	
		% of Total	5.0%	14.0%	19.0%	
Total	Count	88	112	200		
	% of Total	44.0%	56.0%	100.0%		

Grade 1 fatty liver diagnosis, 47 (23.5%) did not have CKD, while 43 (21.5%) did. In Grade 2, 31 individuals (15.5%) did not have CKD, while 41 individuals (20.5%) did. Just 10 (5.0%) of the students in Grade 3 did not have CKD, compared to 28 (14.0%) who did and the p- value 0.026. There may be a link between the severity of the disease and renal involvement, as higher fatty liver grades were frequently linked to a higher frequency of CKD

Table No.3

			Stage of Chronic Kidney disease					Total	p-value	
			.00	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00			
Fatty Liver Grading	1.0	Count	48	22	12	7	1	90	.174	
	0	% of Total	24.0%	11.0%	6.0%	3.5%	0.5%	45.0%		
	2.0	Count	29	20	12	11	0	72		
	0	% of Total	14.5%	10.0%	6.0%	5.5%	0.0%	36.0%		.436
	3.0	Count	10	16	7	5	0	38		
	0	% of Total	5.0%	8.0%	3.5%	2.5%	0.0%	19.0%		.157
Total		count	88	58	31	23	1	200	.167	
		% of Total	43.5%	29.0%	15.5%	11.5%	0.5%	100.0%		

Grade 1 fatty liver advanced to stages 1-4, but the majority (24%) did not have CKD. Grade 2 patients showed similar, with 10% in stage 1 and 14.5% not having CKD, however many (5.5%) had showed to stage 3. There may be a connection between the severity of fatty liver and the progression of chronic kidney disease (CKD), since patients with grade3 fatty liver had higher rates of patients in CKD stages 1 and 2 (8% and 3.5%, respectively). Of those with CKD, 43.5% did not have any CKD at all, and 56.5% were in stages 1-

Discussion:

The purpose of this case-control study was to assess the correlation between the prevalence of chronic kidney disease and the severity of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. Although NAFLD was not a statistically significant predictor of CKD overall (p = 0.742), There was a positive linear trend between increasing NAFLD grade and CKD stage advancement (p = 0.031). These results highlight the significance of fibrosis in NAFLD as opposed to the mere existence of a fatty liver as a cause of renal failure (17) (18) (20) (21)According to Kim et al. (2022), there is an important link between liver fibrosis and chronic kidney disease (CKD). This suggests that, like other risk factors including age, diabetes, and hypertension, CKD risk is increased by more severe liver involvement. Their study employed non-

invasive fibrosis scores (NAFLD-FS). Our study describe 45% of patients having Grade 1 fatty liver, 36% having Grade 2, and 19% having Grade 3, and also discovered a possible correlation between the severity of fatty liver and CKD. Although there was no significant link with CKD stages (p = 0.742), our Chi-square test revealed a significant relationship between fatty liver grading and the presence of CKD (p = 0.026). Both findings highlight the link between a higher incidence of CKD and more severe liver disease. (22) **Propensity Score (PS) Matching Study (n = 3,725) reported** people with NAFLD are more likely to have metabolic risk factors (such as obesity, diabetes, and hypertension), which may exacerbate to CKD. Both studies found that renal outcomes are influenced by the degree of liver fibrosis. Our study only included patients with NAFLD, whereas the PS matching trial individuals with and without NAFLD. Our study excluded the lab data, whereas the PS study examined biochemical markers and a wider range of metabolic indicators. Our study was smaller, hospital-based, whereas the PS study had a bigger and more varied sample size. (23) (24).This idea that simple steatosis may not pose a significant risk to renal health, but progression to more severe liver disease stages like fibrosis or steatohepatitis may initiate or accelerate kidney dysfunction through mechanisms like systemic inflammation, insulin resistance, and activation of the renin-angiotensin

system study's finding that Grade1 NAFLD had the lowest CKD prevalence (47%) without CKD vs (43%) with CKD (25)(26). Furthermore, this needs more research and was not statistically significant in data set ($p = 0.157$), the gender-specific findings in study that CKD was more common in males (41.5%) compared to females (14.5%) may also represent the impact of sex-related metabolic and hormonal differences in NAFLD pathogenesis and CKD vulnerability.(27)(28) Incorporating non-invasive fibrosis measures, such as the NAFLD Fibrosis score . The development of fibrosis, severity, and histologic progression carry a greater load of risk than the simple buildup of hepatic fat. NAFLD is not a binary condition. (29) (30) (31)

Conclusion:

Study concluded that CKD has significant association with fatty liver grading

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